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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE LATEST SALMONELLA TYPHI
SENSITIVITY PATTERN IN THE HOSPITAL****Dr. Rohit Murarka¹, Dr. Madan Giri², Dr. Utsav Bhattarai³**¹ Kathmandu Medical College Teaching Hospital, Nepal, ²Dali University, China, ³Dhulikhel Hospital, Kathmandu University, Nepal.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:**

Introduction: Intestinal fever is very common in Nepal. Multi-drug resistant Salmonella Typhi is popping up all over the world and also in Nepal. Observing the recent pattern of sensitivity will help select the appropriate empirical antibiotics in a resource-constrained country such as Nepal, as cultural facilities are not available nationwide.

Material and methods: The study included 86 S. typhi isolates from blood cultures of patients with suspected typhoid fever who came to the clinic or were admitted to Kathmandu Medical College Teaching Hospital, Nepal for one-year duration from April 2019 to April, 2020.

Results: A total of 86 S. typhi isolates were studied. The mean age of the study population was 22.06 ± 17.1 , with the majority of men 44 (51.2%). All S. typhi isolates were sensitive to Meropenem. The highest resistance was observed to amikacin (62.4%), followed by cotrimoxazole (48.4%) and Amoxiclav (46.5%). S. typhi isolates showed a low level of resistance to ceftriaxone (1.16%), cefuroxime (4.6%), azithromycin (13.9%), levofloxacin (11.6%).

Conclusions: Based on the results of this study, it can be indicated that oral forms of cefuroxime, levofloxacin and azithromycin can be used as the first line. Then, if the patient does not respond, Ceftriaxone can be used. Meropenem should be reserved for selected cases.

Key words: typhoid fever, multi-drug resistance, Salmonella typhi.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Rohit Murarka,**

Kathmandu Medical College Teaching Hospital, Nepal.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

According to WHO, the annual incidence of typhoid fever in the world amounts to 21 million cases, of which 1–4% is fatal [1-2]. It is estimated that 90% of these deaths occur in Asia. In the Indian subcontinent, the highest incidence of typhoid fever is in Nepal (451.7 per 100,000 people / year), followed by India (214.2 per 100,000 people / year) supported that the overall incidence was 3.9 / 1000 people / year, and the proportion was higher in preschool children aged 0-4 years (18.7 per 1000 people / year) [3-4]. Increasing multi-drug resistance with *S. typhi* reduces the effectiveness of treatment, increases treatment costs and results in higher rates of serious complications and deaths. In 1992, the emergence of multi-drug resistance intestinal fever (resistance to chloramphenicol, ampicillin and trimethoprim sulfamethoxazole) was strongly addressed in Nepal; About 36.58% of cases have been reported in a large study [5-6]. Indiscriminate and unwise use of antibiotics increases the risk of newer strains of resistant organisms. Applications of the antibiotic should be based on the culture and sensitivity report. But in Nepal, such facilities are not available throughout the country and the poor cannot afford it [7-8]. Therefore, in most cases, physicians must prescribe empirically. The latest sensitivity pattern will help them choose the most effective drug. It is also important to monitor *S. typhi* susceptibility patterns continuously to ensure appropriate treatment guidelines.

METHODS:

The study included 86 *S. typhi* isolates from blood cultures of patients with suspected typhoid fever who came to the clinic or were admitted to Kathmandu Medical College Teaching Hospital, Nepal for one-year duration from April 2019 to April 2020. Bacterial culture: bile salt broth (broth culture) 5 and

streptokinase broth (clot culture) 6 blood samples were used for enrichment. Enriched samples with visible turbidity were applied to Mac-Conkey, XLD and Wilson Blair media. Isolates producing characteristic colonies were identified by conventional biochemical tests using API20E and confirmed by agglutination with Salmonella O9, Vi and Hd antisera. Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing: Antimicrobial susceptibility testing was performed using the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method in accordance with the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS) guidelines 7 using ampicillin (10 µg / disk), Amoxiclav, Azithromycin, Levofloxacin, Chloramphenicol (30 µg / disk), Cotrimoxazole (1.25-23.75 µg / disk), ciprofloxacin (5 µg / disk), cefuroxime, cefixime, ceftriaxone (5 µg / disk), nalidixic acid (30 µg / disk) and meropenem (10 µg / disk). *Escherichia coli* ATCC 25922 was used as a negative control and *S. typhi* MTCC 734 was used as a positive control for antibiotic disk performance. Commercial disks -with a diameter of 6 mm were used. Isolates resistant to ampicillin, chloramphenicol and cotrimoxazole have been reported to be multi-drug resistant (MDR).

RESULTS:

A total of 86 *S. typhi* isolates were included in the study. The mean age of the study population was 22.06 ± 17.1, with the majority of men 44 (51.2%). Antibiogram of these isolates showed that all *S. typhi* isolates were sensitive to Meropenem. The highest resistance was observed to amikacin (62.4%), followed by cotrimoxazole (48.4%) and Amoxiclav (46.5%). *S. typhi* isolates showed a low level of resistance to ceftriaxone (1.16%), cefuroxime (4.6%), azithromycin (13.9%), levofloxacin (11.6%). Approximately 24.4% (N = 21) of the isolates had MDR.

Table-I
Number of *S. typhi* isolates resistant to antibiotics by disc diffusion method

Antibiotic screened	No of resistant isolate	Percentage
Amoxiclav	40	46.5
Azithromycin	12	13.9
Amikacin	54	62.8
Cefuroxime	4	4.6
Cefixime	20	23.2
Ceftriaxone	1	1.16
Ciprofloxacin	30	34.8
Co-trimoxazole	42	48.4
Gentamicin	12	13.9
Chloramphenicol	28	32.5
Levofloxacin	10	11.6
Meropenem	0	0
MDR	21	24.4

MDR = Multidrug resistant

DISCUSSION:

Due to a combination of factors including poor sanitation and healthcare infrastructure, typhoid fever remains a major public health problem in most resource-poor countries such as Nepal [9-10]. Most studies have shown that enteric fever occurs mainly in the pediatric age group, but in this study the mean age of the patient was 22 years due to the increased number of adult patients [11-12]. According to the records of public and private hospitals, intestinal fever is the main infectious disease in this region with a high fluctuating frequency. The data presented in our study highlights that there is a high percentage of MDR [13-14]. The presence of MDR (i.e., resistance to ampicillin, chloramphenicol and cotrimoxazole) was 24.4%. This result is consistent with other reports from the same regions. Meropenem has no immunity [15]. Ceftriaxone is still very sensitive, although it is expensive and only available as an injection. Among the oral forms, the most effective are cefuroxime, levofloxacin and azithromycin.

CONCLUSIONS:

Drug resistance developed as a result of the unwise and massive use of antibiotics. Caution should be exercised in selecting antibiotics when used empirically. According to the results of this study, oral formulations of cefuroxime, levofloxacin and azithromycin may be recommended as the first line. Then, if the patient does not respond, Ceftriaxone can be used. Meropenem should be reserved for selected cases.

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